

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHANGES IN THE LEVELS OF SOME INTERLEUKINS DURING TOXOPLASMA GONDII INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

Opportunistic infections (OI) are infections that most commonly occur in immunocompromised people and are more severe in those with weakened immune systems. These types of infections can be caused by a variety of pathogens, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and parasites. In people with normal immune systems, opportunistic infections are less likely to cause harm, usually resulting in mild infections and no impact. However, studies have shown that the immune system can undergo significant changes during OI (including a decrease in the number and function of immune cells such as T-lymphocytes and natural killer cells). These changes can lead to a reduced ability to fight infections, which leads to increased morbidity and mortality.

Several studies have examined the changes in the immune system that occur during OI. Studies have shown that OI can cause a number of immune system dysfunctions, including decreased production of cytokines and chemokines. During parasitic infection, lymphocytes produce specific cytokines that play an important role in the defense against parasitic diseases. For example, IL-6 leads to the production of antibodies and has a proinflammatory effect through the induction of acute phase protein production. In addition, IL-10 and IL-6 affect the type of immune response by inhibiting the production of proinflammatory cytokines. Among these infections, *Toxoplasma gondii* was investigated and information was collected about the cytokine (IL4, IL6, IL8, IL10) changes that occur in the body during this infection.

Keywords: *Toxoplasma gondii*, IL4, IL6, IL8, IL10, uveitis.

Introduction.

Toxoplasma gondii is a protozoan parasite that infects approximately one-third of the world's population. In immunocompromised individuals, such as those with AIDS, those receiving chemotherapy or immunosuppressive drugs, *Toxoplasma gondii* infection can cause symptomatic and fatal toxoplasmosis [1].

T. gondii is a food- and water-borne parasite capable of infecting all nucleated cells. The prevalence of toxoplasmosis varies widely, from 5% to 90%, depending on the region and environment. The disease is influenced by climatic conditions, consumption habits (e.g., consumption of raw meat or unwashed fruits and vegetables), and environmental hygiene standards, with

prevalence generally higher in warm and humid climates [2].

Once *T. gondii* cysts enter the human body, the parasites differentiate into tachyzoites, which enter the bloodstream and can infect any organ. Finally, the tachyzoites enter the brain, where they gradually transform into bradyzoites and form lifelong tissue cysts [3].

T. gondii transforms into a slow-growing form (bradyzoite) that evades host immune responses and causes chronic infection. Thus, immunological balance between the healthy host and *T. gondii* is considered a key step in the immunobiology of *T. gondii*.

T. gondii infection activates both humoral and cellular immunity. Cellular immune responses, which are

part of the defense system, are important for the management of intracellular infections such as toxoplasmosis. In response to *T. gondii* infection, activation of type 2 cytokines such as IL-4 and IL-10 leads to increased susceptibility, whereas IFN- γ cytokines mediate resistance by activating macrophages to suppress the parasite [4].

Toxoplasma gondii infection is a common cause of posterior uveitis in immunocompetent individuals [5]. *Toxoplasma retinochoroiditis* is a major determinant of visual impairment, accounting for 30–55% of posterior uveitis cases, particularly in areas with high *T. gondii* infection in the United States and Europe (6). The incidence of ocular toxoplasmosis increases significantly with age.

Patients older than 35 years and with a history of posterior uveitis should be considered at risk for primary intraocular lymphoma (PIOL). This malignant lymphoproliferation exhibits clinical features similar to ocular infections, including ocular toxoplasmosis [7].

Determination of an IL-10/IL-6 interleukin ratio greater than 1 has recently been useful in the diagnosis of PIOL (intraocular lenses that are surgically implanted in the eye to correct refractive errors without removing the natural lens), especially in cases where the predictive value of cytology is poor.

In another study, the medical records of 4 patients (3 males and 1 female) with panuveitis were reviewed and tear cytokine levels, along with humoral and cellular responses, were evaluated for the differential diagnosis of PIOL. This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

The diagnosis of ocular toxoplasmosis was made based on the sudden onset of visual symptoms, the presence of specific inflammation or hyperpigmentation scars in the retina and choroid, and laboratory evidence of *T. gondii* infection. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was performed to determine serum IgG/IgM antibodies to *T. gondii*. The cut-off for IgG antibodies to *T. gondii* was as follows: 1) negative, rate <0.8 IU/ml; borderline 0.8-1.1 IU/ml; 2) positive, rate >1.1 IU/ml. The cut-off for IgM antibodies to *T. gondii* was as follows: 1) negative, rate <0.8 IU/ml; borderline 0.8-1.1 IU/ml; 2) positive, rate >1.1 IU/ml. The presence of *T. gondii* in tear and blood samples was determined by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis.

The study identified a case of mixed panuveitis in a 4-year-old patient with no comorbidities. Two of them (cases 1 and 2) had already been diagnosed with ARN and cytomegalovirus (CMV) retinitis at a local ophthalmology clinic. A panel of laboratory tests was performed for differential diagnosis and anti-*Toxoplasma* IgG antibodies were detected in tears and *T. gondii* DNA in all study patients. Elevated IL-10 levels and IL10/IL-6 ratios were also noted in 4 patients. This is also indicative of PIOL. Levels of certain cytokines may be useful in differentiating PIOL from uveitis. High levels of IL-6 secreted by inflammatory cells are characteristic of uveitis, while high levels of IL-10 production by B lymphocytes are characteristic of intraocular and central nervous system lymphoma [8].

In addition, an IL-10/IL-6 ratio greater than 1 has been strongly associated with PIOL; however, the use

of the IL-10/IL-6 ratio for the diagnosis of PIOL is controversial, as elevated IL-10 and IL-6 levels have also been reported in eyes with non-neoplastic uveitis [9,10]. Cytokines secreted by lymphocytes play an important role in the development of parasitic diseases. For example, IL-6 levels in individuals infected with *T. gondii* are approximately doubled compared to healthy individuals, indicating the presence of an inflammatory state caused by the parasite. Moreover, IL-10 levels have been shown to be 5-fold higher in individuals with toxoplasmosis than in those without. During acute *T. gondii* infection, IL-10 plays a crucial role by inhibiting cellular (IL-12, TNF- α) and inflammatory (IL-6) responses [11,12]. IL-10 can help reduce the negative effects of the inflammatory response and dampen the immune system, which is beneficial for both the host and the parasite [13].

It is likely that patients infected with *T. gondii* may exhibit similar cytokine levels due to an equivalent humoral response. Therefore, in the absence of definitive pathological evidence of lymphoma, PIOL cannot be easily concluded from cytokine profile results alone, especially if ocular toxoplasmosis has not been ruled out.

Toxoplasma gondii infection in pregnant women can cause congenital disorders in the fetus and newborns. In healthy individuals, *T. gondii* infection is asymptomatic because the mother's innate and adaptive immunity resists its initial spread and destroys most of the parasites. *T. gondii* tachyzoites (the rapidly growing form of *T. gondii*) strongly induce innate immune responses such as the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines by monocytes, resulting in the activation of adaptive immune responses mediated by T and B cells. Activation of adaptive immunity further stimulates cell-autonomous immune responses in infected cells, which disrupt intracellular growth of the protozoan and mediate its clearance. Studies have also shown that some indicators have been observed in pregnant women, as well as in patients with other diseases. *Toxoplasma* infection causes abortion or congenital anomalies (hydrocephalus and retinochoroiditis) in more susceptible pregnant women [14]. The immune system mounts a protective immune response based on the interaction of antigen with antigen-presenting cells (APCs), which induces the transduction of nuclear factor kappa (NF- κ B) to initiate the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL1b, IL12, etc.) [15,16].

Host lymphocytes and myeloid cells not only secrete a network of cytokines for signaling pathways when exposed to antigen, but also upregulate certain chemokines and Toll-like receptors (TLRs) on their surfaces to act against any signaling antigen [17].

In response to specific intracellular signals, various pro-inflammatory (IL1 β , IL12, IL18, TNF α , IFN γ) and anti-inflammatory (IL4, IL10, TGF β) cytokines induce an immune response that develops resistance or an immune response to the specific response of cytokines. This suggests that IL-8 levels are increased in pregnant women with toxoplasmosis and that this increase may be an indicator of adverse effects on the fetus.

Another study reported that *T. gondii* infection increased IL-12 levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. Although no specific data were provided on IL-8 levels,

the relationship between IL-12 and IL-8 should be considered.

As a result of the research conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Studies of cytokine production in patients with *Toxoplasma gondii* infection showed that, compared to healthy individuals, there is a noticeable increase in the synthesis of IL-6 and IL-10 cytokines during exacerbations of the disease. In parallel, with the positive dynamics of the disease, the level of cytokines gradually begins to decrease.

2. The balance of the antibodies depends on the severity of the disease; as the disease worsens, the level of antibodies also increases.

3. Studying the stock balance allows us to understand the pathogenesis of the infection, the tropism and virulence of the virus, thereby helping to develop a control system for toxoplasmosis infection.

We are studying the dynamics of changes in the levels of some interleukins during opportunistic infections. We hope that our findings will be reflected in research in this direction.

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